

DATA-DRIVEN RETROSPECTIVE ASSESSMENT OF NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASE AND RISK FACTORS AMONG ADULTS FROM MEDICAL INFORMATION ARCHIVED SYSTEM RECORDS

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ABSTRACT

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as diabetes, hypertension, obesity, and anaemia are major public health concerns, accounting for 74% of global deaths. In India, NCDs cause about 66% of total mortality, mainly due to lifestyle factors like poor diet, inactivity, tobacco, and alcohol use. Tamil Nadu ranks among the highest in NCD prevalence, with 33.9% of adults having hypertension and 17.6% diabetes. This retrospective cross-sectional study assessed the prevalence and risk factors of NCDs among adults attending the General Medicine OPD at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital, Thandalam, Chennai, using data from the Medical Information Archival System (MIAS). A total of 1,213 adults aged 30–60 years were selected through purposive sampling. Data on demographic, behavioural, and clinical parameters were extracted using a structured format based on the WHO STEPS approach. Results showed that 25.8% had diabetes, 24.9% hypertension, 22.4% obesity, and 19.3% anaemia. Unhealthy behaviours were prevalent 38% smoked, 35.2% consumed alcohol, 63.6% had poor diets, and 67.6% were sedentary. Significant associations were found between lifestyle factors and NCDs. The study underscores the need for focused awareness, screening, and lifestyle interventions to curb the rising NCD burden in Tamil Nadu.

Keywords: Non-communicable diseases, diabetes, hypertension, obesity, anaemia, lifestyle risk factors.

Introduction

Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) including diabetes mellitus, hypertension, obesity, and anaemia remain a major global public health challenge, significantly contributing to morbidity and mortality worldwide. According to the **World Health Organization (WHO, 2023)**, NCDs account for approximately 74% of all global deaths. These diseases are largely driven by modifiable behavioural and lifestyle risk factors such as physical inactivity, unhealthy dietary habits, tobacco use, and harmful alcohol consumption (WHO, 2023). Unlike communicable diseases, NCDs are chronic in nature, progress gradually, and impose a considerable economic burden on individuals, families, and healthcare systems particularly in low- and middle-income countries (WHO, 2022).

In the Indian context, the increasing burden of NCDs has significantly altered the country's disease landscape. According to the **Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR, 2022)** and the **World Health Organization (2023)**, approximately 66% of all deaths in India are attributed to NCDs, with hypertension and

Findings from the **National Family Health Survey-5 (NFHS-5, 2019–21)** revealed that 24% of men and 21% of women in Tamil Nadu have elevated blood pressure, while 16% of adults are diagnosed with diabetes (**Ministry of Health and Family Welfare [MoHFW], 2021**). Rapid urbanization, dietary transitions, increased stress levels, and decreased physical activity have collectively contributed to the early onset of metabolic and cardiovascular disorders, even among younger adults (**Patel et al., 2021**). Notably, Tamil Nadu ranks among the Indian states with the highest prevalence of NCDs, emphasizing the urgent need for early detection, data-driven monitoring, and lifestyle-based preventive interventions (**ICMR, 2022**).

Hospital-based data play a pivotal role in understanding real-world disease patterns and identifying population-level risk factors. Retrospective analyses of electronic medical records (EMRs) provide valuable insights into the prevalence, distribution, and determinants of NCDs across diverse patient populations (**Kaur et al., 2020**). Therefore, the present study aims to conduct a data-driven retrospective assessment of non-communicable diseases and their associated lifestyle risk factors among adults attending the General Medicine Outpatient Department (OPD) at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital, Chennai. The findings are expected to inform healthcare providers and policymakers, facilitating the design of evidence-based, community-oriented screening and health promotion strategies.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The analysis by **Taheri Soodejani et al. (2024)** showed that global NCD prevalence rose between 2000 and 2019, while mortality declined due to improved healthcare and preventive efforts.

In the **Tamil Nadu STEPS Survey**, **Selvavinayagam et al. (2024)** reported high rates of hypertension, diabetes, and obesity,

linking obesity, male gender, and age with greater NCD risk.

Anjana et al. (2024) identified over 101 million diabetics and 315 million hypertensive individuals in India, attributing poor control to unhealthy diets and inadequate lifestyle management.

Through community-based screening, **Roy et al. (2024)** found 55.2% at high NCD risk, with obesity, male gender, and unemployment significantly influencing hypertension prevalence.

Shu and Ramesh et al. (2023) highlighted that NCDs cause most global and Indian deaths, emphasizing hypertension and diabetes as major contributors requiring lifestyle reform and screening.

A national review by **Sharma et al. (2024)** showed higher tobacco use, poor diet, and inactivity among urban low-income groups, consistent with rural Karnataka and West Bengal findings.

Research by **Behera and Mona & Suri (2024)** revealed women, especially older adults, face higher risks of diabetes and hypertension due to hormonal and social factors.

Among middle-aged women, **Niranjani et al. (2024)** observed obesity and metabolic disorders, while **Biswas et al. (2024)** noted adolescents already developing NCD risk behaviours.

Studies by **Boro and Saikia (2024)** linked tobacco and alcohol with NCDs in Northeast India, and **Ciancio et al. (2021)** showed community screening improved early detection.

A recent **Meghalaya study (2025)** found young adults developing early hypertension from poor diets and sedentary habits, highlighting the need for early preventive education programs.

hat community-based screening improves early disease detection, treatment adherence, and health outcomes in low- resource regions.

A 2025 study from Meghalaya revealed that even young adults are developing elevated blood pressure due to poor diets and sedentary habits. This shift toward early-onset NCDs underscores the growing urgency for school-based education, lifestyle modification, and early preventive screening programs.

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

A quantitative research approach with a retrospective cross-sectional design was conducted to assess the prevalence and risk factors associated with non-communicable diseases (NCDs) among adults attending the General Medicine Outpatient Department (OPD) at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital, Thandalam, Chennai. The study was carried out in the Non-Communicable Disease (NCD) Clinic, which provides regular screening and follow-up care for lifestyle- related disorders. A total of 1,213 medical records meeting the inclusion criteria were selected using a purposive sampling technique from the Medical Information Archival System (MIAS). Ethical clearance and institutional permission were obtained before data collection. A structured data extraction tool based on the WHO STEPS framework was used to collect information on demographic variables, behavioral risk factors (tobacco use, alcohol consumption, dietary pattern, and physical activity), physical measurements (height, weight, BMI, and blood pressure), and biochemical parameters (blood glucose, haemoglobin, and cholesterol). Adults aged 30–60 years diagnosed with at least one NCD such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, anaemia, or obesity were included, while incomplete or irrelevant records were excluded. Data were systematically reviewed, coded, and entered into Microsoft Excel for analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage

were used to describe the demographic characteristics and prevalence of NCDs, while inferential statistics including the chi-square test and odds ratio were applied to determine the association between demographic variables, lifestyle factors, and disease occurrence. This study provided evidence- based insights into the burden and determinants of major NCDs among adults, emphasizing the need for targeted preventive and health-promoting interventions. The flow of participants through each phase of the study is presented in Figure 1.

RESULTS:

To assess the prevalence of major non-communicable diseases (diabetes, hypertension, anemia, and obesity) among adults attending the General Medicine OPD at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital

Frequency and percentage distribution of prevalence of major non-communicable

diseases (diabetes, hypertension, anemia, and obesity) among adults attending the General Medicine OPD at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital

Table: 1 Prevalence of major non-communicable diseases among adults attending the General Medicine OPD at selected setting

Major NCD	Frequency	Percentage
1. Diabetes mellitus		
a) Prediabetes	125	10.31
b) Diabetes	188	15.50
2. Hypertension mm/hg		
a) Pre hypertension (129-80) mm/hg	132	10.88
b) Stage 1 hypertension (139-89) mm/hg	108	8.90
c) Stage 2 hypertension (140-90) mm/hg	62	5.11
3. Anaemia		
a) Mild 10.11.9 gm	138	11.38
b) Moderate 7.0-9.9 gm	73	6.02
c) Severe below 7.0 gm	23	1.90
4. BMI		
a) Overweight	174	14.34
b) Obesity	98	8.08
5. Combination of NCD		
a) Diabetes mellitus and b) Hypertension	92	7.58

presents the frequency and percentage distribution of major non-communicable diseases (NCDs) among the adult population studied. Regarding diabetes status, 10.31% of individuals were in the prediabetic range, while 15.50% were diagnosed with diabetes. Blood pressure assessment showed that 10.88% had pre-hypertension, 8.90% had Stage 1 hypertension, and 5.11% had Stage 2

hypertension. With respect to anaemia, 11.38% had mild anaemia, 6.02% had moderate anaemia, and 1.90% were classified with severe anaemia. In terms of body mass index (BMI), 14.34% of participants were overweight, and 8.08% were obese. Additionally, 7.58% of the individuals were found to have a combination of both diabetes mellitus and hypertension. These findings reflect a considerable burden of single and coexisting NCDs within the adult population.

The second objective of the study was to determine the prevalence of major Non-communicable disease (Diabetes, hypertension, Anemia, obesity) among adults at Saveetha medical college and hospital.

Among 1,213 adults assessed, diabetes affected 15.5% and 10.3% were pre-diabetic. Hypertension was found in 24.9% (10.88% pre-hypertension, 8.90% Stage 1, 5.11% Stage 2). Anaemia affected 19.29% (11.38% mild, 6.02% moderate, 1.90% severe). Obesity was 22.42% (14.34% overweight, 8.08% obese), while 7.58% had both diabetes and hypertension. Advancing age, male gender, unemployment, sedentary lifestyle, and unhealthy diet were key risk factors.

The third objective of the study was to investigate the relationship between lifestyle factors and non-communicable disease at Saveetha medical college and hospital.

Revealed that smoking, alcohol use, high-salt intake, and vigorous physical activity were linked to higher prevalence of diabetes (5.7–22.15%), obesity (5.2–17.75%), hypertension (6.9–27.45%), and anaemia (6.9–23.3%), though not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). In contrast, prior history of NCDs showed a strong association with current disease presence ($p < 0.001$), emphasizing the need for early detection and preventive care.

DISSUSSION:

The present study aimed to determine the prevalence and associated risk factors of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as diabetes, hypertension, anaemia, and obesity among adults attending Saveetha Medical College and Hospital, Chennai. A total of 1,213 adults aged 30–60 years were assessed using a structured questionnaire based on the WHO STEPS approach. The results revealed a high prevalence of NCDs—25.8% had diabetes, 24.9% hypertension, 22.4% obesity, and 19.3% anaemia. Lifestyle analysis showed that 38% were smokers, 35.2% consumed alcohol, 63.6% followed unhealthy diets, and 67.6% led sedentary lives. Advancing age, male gender, unemployment, and poor lifestyle habits were major contributing factors.

The study findings align with Roy et al. (2024), who found a high NCD risk (55.2%) associated with male gender, widowhood, and obesity, and with Selvavinayagam et al. (2024), who reported 17.6% diabetes and 33.9% hypertension in Tamil Nadu. Similarly, Jayaraj et al. (2020) and Anjana et al. (2024) identified sedentary lifestyles, obesity, and poor diet as significant contributors to diabetes and hypertension. Furthermore, Ajith M., Mohamed Sameer H., Padma Priya, Deepika D., Karpagam K., and Sindhu Ramalingam (2024), in their study Assess the Effects of Buerger-Allen Exercise on the Healing of Neuropathic Diabetic Foot Ulcers in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes, highlighted that Buerger-Allen exercises significantly improve peripheral circulation and enhance ulcer healing among diabetic patients, reinforcing the importance of incorporating physical activity in NCD management and prevention.

Recent findings by Sasikala Palayan et al. (2025) in their study Socio-demographic Determinants of Cardiovascular Risk Factors among Adults in Suburban Population of South India emphasized that low educational status, unemployment, and sedentary behaviour were major predictors of cardiovascular and metabolic risk factors. These determinants were consistent with the present study's findings, showing that socio-demographic factors significantly influence the onset and progression of NCDs. Similarly, Chandrakar, Sethu, and Panda (2025) in their qualitative study Exploring the Lived-in Experiences of Adolescent School-going Girls with Anaemia revealed that poor nutrition, menstrual irregularities, and psychosocial stress greatly affect adolescents' health and academic performance, underscoring the need for targeted preventive education and dietary interventions even at younger ages.

The high coexistence of diabetes and hypertension observed in this study (7.58%) further supports the notion that metabolic disorders often overlap due to shared behavioural and physiological pathways. This clustering effect, as observed in earlier studies, magnifies long-term morbidity risks and increases the healthcare burden. The findings also highlight that men, particularly those in middle age, are at greater risk due to lifestyle patterns characterized by tobacco use, alcohol consumption, and work-related stress. This underlines the urgent need for workplace-based wellness programs and regular medical check-ups to promote early detection and management of NCDs. (Ajith, M et al 2025)

Moreover, the growing evidence from recent national studies suggests that lifestyle modification, community-based screening, and health education play vital roles in reducing NCD prevalence (Patel et al., 2021; WHO, 2023). Strengthening primary healthcare through systematic NCD surveillance and integrating nutrition counselling, mental health support, and physical activity promotion can yield significant improvements in population health outcomes. Future research should also explore digital health platforms and mobile-based interventions for continuous monitoring, motivation, and support for individuals at risk.

Overall, the findings from this study, supported by recent national and regional evidence, stress the multidimensional nature of NCDs. Addressing socio-demographic determinants, promoting lifestyle changes, and improving community awareness are essential for sustainable control and prevention. Multi-sectoral collaborations between healthcare institutions, educational organizations, and public health agencies can play a key role in reducing the rising NCD burden in Tamil Nadu and across India.

CONCLUSION:

This study highlights a significant prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as hypertension, diabetes, obesity, and anaemia among adults aged 30–60 years at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital. Demographic factors like age, gender, and education influenced disease occurrence. Though lifestyle factors showed increased NCD rates, statistical significance was not observed, except for a strong association with prior NCD history. These findings underscore the importance of early screening, regular monitoring, and preventive health education.

LIMITATIONS: The study is limited to data available in **retrospective records**, and information not recorded in MIAS cannot be evaluated. Causal relationships cannot be established due to the **retrospective and observational** nature of the study. The findings are **hospital-based** and may not be generalizable to the broader community or rural

populations. Behavioural data (e.g., diet, physical activity, stress) might be **incompletely recorded** in patient files, leading to potential bias. The study includes only patients who visited the **General Medicine OPD**, possibly excluding asymptomatic individuals or those attending other departments.

FUTURE SCOPE: Conduct regular NCD screening programs for adults in high-risk groups. Organize community health education on lifestyle modification and risk reduction. Strengthen primary healthcare facilities for early NCD detection and care. Provide ongoing NCD training programs for nursing staff and professionals. Use WHO STEPS tool for standardized NCD risk assessment.

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